

D3.3 SPOT-IT Tool (Final version)

(IT = Innovative Tool)

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Purpose and scope of the deliverable

The SPOT-IT tool is designed to provide decision-supporting information for various stakeholders who are interesting in promoting cultural tourism within a given case study area.

The tool is based on GIS layers, a decision supporting mechanism, two additional algorithms, and a public participation platform.

Document history

Version	Date	Description
<i>0.1</i>	<i>15-Aug-2022</i>	<i>The first draft delivered to PMB</i>
	<i>23-Aug-2022</i>	<i>Teams' feedback, comments and complements</i>
<i>0.2</i>	<i>24-Aug-2022</i>	<i>Deliverable report and SPOT-IT documentation (manual, tutorial kits, etc.) drafted and submitted to PMB</i>
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<i>1.0</i>	<i>31-Aug-2022</i>	<i>The final version of the document prepared and uploaded to SYGMA Portal</i>

Content

1	<u>About SPOT-IT tool</u>	4
1.1	<u>Purposes of the tool</u>	4
	<u>Overall description</u>	4
2	<u>Main components of SPOT-IT</u>	5
2.1	<u>GIS layers</u>	5
2.2	<u>Decision supporting information</u>	6
	<u>Layer by layer summation</u>	6
	<u>Annual visitors forecast</u>	6
2.3	<u>Public Engagement Platform</u>	6
3	<u>Design progress in 2022</u>	7
3.1	<u>The overall state of the art of SPOT-IT</u>	7
3.2	<u>Advancement of SPOT-IT technology and new components</u>	8
4	<u>Deliverables</u>	9
4.1	<u>SPOT-IT tools and manuals</u>	9
	<u>Public engagement platform</u>	9
	<u>SPOT-IT User Manual</u>	9
	<u>Video tutorial</u>	10
	<u>Localizing the tool – Tool’s administrator instructions</u>	10
	<u>Localizing the tool - Hands-on workshop video</u>	10

1 About SPOT-IT tool

1.1 Purposes of the tool

The main aim of WP3 is to develop an innovative tool that could provide decision support mechanisms for the development of cultural heritage attractions/sites.

The purposes of this tool are:

1. To enable the sustainable development of cultural tourism which takes into account the interest of multiple stakeholders (i.e. ethnic and cultural minorities, peripheral and de-industrialized areas, etc.).
2. To suggest strategies for establishing, promoting, and marketing new and existing attractions based on reference to the best practice of other cultural tourism sites in other regions with similar characteristics/conditions.
3. To promote research on applications of advanced technologies (i.e., Geospatial artificial intelligence and machine learning) in the domain of tourism in general and in cultural tourism in particular.
4. To Pilot and improve the tool so that it can be disseminated and possibly commercialized during the duration of the project.
5. To enable localities interested in developing cultural tourism to be able to systematically assess their potential, identify gaps and barriers.
6. To enable sponsors, local authorities, and entrepreneurs to be able to evaluate the development potential of a given cultural heritage asset.
7. To enable given resources and target communities to be identified and incorporated in a chosen project.
8. To reveal the area's potential for tourism development; to present not only the sites that have already gained interest and cultural tourist activity but also those that have not yet been developed.

Overall description

SPOT-IT tool (IT, Innovative Tool) is a web-based collaborative platform aimed at providing a framework of decision-making supporting information for facilitating cultural heritage tourism development. Its major purpose is to realize the existing and future potential in the fields of cultural heritage tourism to promote local and regional development. The tool is targeted at stakeholders at all levels, who can benefit (or suffer) from promoting local and regional development and for those who consider the development of cultural tourism as a major catalyst for sustainable development and an increased sense of Europeanisation. These stakeholders include but are not limited to, entrepreneurs, investors, residents, and local, regional, and national authorities.

The tool functions as a collaborative platform. It makes use of GIS layers that reflect numerous cultural tourism-related data. These data can be categorized into two types of INPUT data:

- **Primary data**, i.e., data that were collected directly from main sources through interviews with experts, officials, local residents regarding their knowledge and experience. These data were collected via surveys, roundtable discussions, etc.
- **Secondary data**, i.e., censuses, information collected by government departments and other official organizations, online consumer reviews, and other social media content, or planners' records

Most of the data were used for designing GIS layers. Online consumer reviews and other social media data were analyzed and processed by automatic procedures (e.g., Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning), and primary data collected via surveys were analyzed via Semi-automatic rule-based procedures in which the end-user is being asked to provide additional inputs. The final output of these stages will allow well-informed cultural tourism-related decision-making by end-users.

The OUTPUTS include scoring and rankings of geographical pixels based on their suitability for cultural tourism development that accounts for economic, environmental, and social considerations. In addition, the outputs include forecasts regarding the expected annual visitors of a suggested cultural tourism venture, based on user's input and place-specific data. The tool also allows for local, cultural tourism, bottom-up initiatives to materialize via public participation platforms.

The design of the tool started as a specific Israeli case study. Since its inception, it has been further developed, and technologically advanced, and more data were acquired. It is now ready to be expanded and adjusted for all other countries participating in the SPOT project. In its final shape, SPOT-IT will be an effective apparatus that will serve multiple stakeholders in the various spheres of cultural tourism to acquire creative information (otherwise scattered in numerous places) and insights into the current state of (local and regional) cultural tourism development. The tool will enable these stakeholders to make sustained decisions regarding future development while considering environmental and social perspectives (i.e., social needs of certain vulnerable groups including minority races and the elderly). Below we describe the progress achieved so far as well as future stages (section 3).

2 Main components of SPOT-IT

2.1 GIS layers

The below-listed layers can be modified and extended based on the partners' opinion, needs and availability of information and data.

- a. **Land use planning** – Distinguishes between several land use categories including Residential; Commercial and Service; Industrial; Transportation; Industrial and Commercial Complexes and Recreational. This layer enables the end-user to identify geographical locations (pixels) that can be suitable for cultural tourism development.
- b. **Distance in km. from the nearest metropolis** – Distance surface map showing distance from each pixel to the nearest metropolis (this layer will be integrated to the EU countries' tool). Due to the limited area of the Israeli case study (where 20 km is the furthest distance) this layer has not been included in the demo version.
- c. **Accessibility to transport** – A map indicating locations of intercity bus routes and stations, train stations, exit on the highway. (In the Israeli case study area there is only one highway for the entire case study).
- d. **Cultural/heritage tourism sites in the region** – Distinguished by each site's theme. This layer can identify agglomeration or clusters of cultural sites, the potential for generating complementarities, and compatibilities.
- e. **Cultural/heritage tourism potential (cultural stock)** – this refers to cultural points of interest which have not been developed, categorized by three levels of interest: 1. To local visitors; 2. To National/regional visitors; 3. To international visitors. This layer is based on cultural tourism experts' opinions.

- f. **Complementarity tourism infrastructure** (hotels, restaurants, other touristic attractions) – in the case study area. This layer can help identify tourism 'hot spots' and highlight available facilities activities and visitor attractions in the area.
- g. **Potential social and environmental conflicts factor** – mapping locations of potential conflicts which might hamper the development of (certain types) cultural tourism sites and activities. Potential sources of conflicts: between new and old comers, ultra-orthodox and secular populations, different nationalities, socio-economic classes, or conflicts over the use of natural resources. These data were derived from stakeholders and expert opinions.
- h. **Environmental vulnerability** - mapping locations in which vulnerable/fragile eco-systems, important habitats, endangered species, and ecological corridors exist. These data were retrieved from Israel's National Terrestrial Biodiversity Assessment Program, and the Open Landscape Institute (OLI) of Israel.
- i. **Microclimate conditions** – a number of inter-related factors that characterize the local micro-climate are: Temperature, solar radiation, wind distribution, wind speed, and relative humidity. These conditions, jointly, are responsible for thermal comfort. A mapping of these conditions was done such that each pixel's thermal comfort was ranked compared to the optimal thermal comfort conditions in the particular country. [The data for this layer was received from the Israel Meteorological Services].
- j. **User-Generated Content:** two different layers based on online consumers' contributions include: landscape heat maps, and sentiment map. These layers were created by employing machine learning algorithm in order to analyze the online reviews and images retrieved from social media and tourism websites in 2019 (prior to the outbreak of Covid-19).

2.2 Decision supporting information

Layer by layer summation

All layers (excluding layer h. which refers to social conflicts) are ranked on a scale (1-5 or 1-3) where the lowest level indicates the least favorable conditions for cultural tourism development and the highest level indicates the most favorable conditions. For example, for the micro-climate layer, a score of 1 is endowed to pixels with a 'very hot' categorization. This component allows to create a map where each pixel is characterized by a (layer-by-layer) summation of these scales. Pixels with the highest total score are presumed to have favorable conditions across all combined layers and vice versa.

Annual visitors forecast

The tool is equipped with an algorithm that returns the predicted number of annual visitors for a potential cultural tourism site at a chosen geographical point (pixel) in the case-study area. The function is based on the features of the chosen location (e.g., population density, distance from nature reserves within a certain radius) as well as characteristics of the designated tourism site as defined by the user. The annual number of visitors is a good proxy for a site's prospected revenue. The function that returns the expected annual visitors was estimated on Israeli market-based data collected in 2015 and 2018 of visitors' attractions in the rural space. The function was drawn from an adapted version of the rural attractions equilibrium model (demand and pricing equations) developed by Hatan, Fleischer & Tchetchik, 2021¹. Some EU market-based data on

¹ Hatan, S., Fleischer, A., & Tchetchik, A. (2021). Economic valuation of cultural ecosystem services: The case of landscape aesthetics in the agritourism market. *Ecological Economics*, 184, 107005.

cultural tourism has been collected by the partners, and the model can be readily estimated based on the adapted model for each country.

2.3 Public Engagement Platform

This platform is linked to the tool. It was indicated that SPOT would be the first ever project to work with local communities, to empower them and put them in charge of Cultural Tourism through co-design with local Stakeholders. The intention is to contribute to the Europeanisation of culture 'from below' by recognizing place identity through the involvement and engagement of local communities and organisations in protecting and presenting their own cultural heritage.

3 Design progress in 2022

3.1 The overall state of the art of SPOT-IT

The first step was to develop the concept of the innovative tool (SPOT-IT) as a decision-supporting mechanism by identifying its main objectives, the stakeholders it is expected to serve, data availability and, finally, based on these inputs, to design the tool's concept, its components and how they will interact with each other.

The tool has been designed to provide multi-criteria decision-supporting information for various stakeholders who are interested in promoting cultural tourism within a given area. The tool has been first developed and tested on an ArcGIS Server that we deployed on the Microsoft Azure: Cloud Computing Services. After the testing period, in order to cut the expenses, we converted to on-premises deployment.

Features and components implemented so far include the following:

- 1) GIS layers were established. The layers are based on the most important criteria for cultural tourism development. Some of these layers are fundamental to all case studies, and some can be flexible according to the case study area's unique characteristics and the availability of the required data.
- 2) A decision-supporting mechanism-based criterion/layer has been programmed and incorporated into the tool. It is aimed to allow decision-makers to have a comparative point of view.
- 3) Two additional algorithms that were designed are based on:
 - a) Prediction function that retrieves the predicted number of annual visitors for a suggested cultural tourism site at a specific location within the case study region.
 - b) Data with relevance to tourism development was retrieved from social media and social networks in its raw format. This data included images and texts which were then analyzed via big data methods (e.g., machine learning) to create a landscape characterization layer and sentiment analysis-based layer.
- 4) Public engagements platform. The Community Collaboration application was integrated into the tool and tested. It is intended for the general public. This application should enable community members, stakeholders, tourists, or whoever wants to propose or reflect on potential cultural heritage sites or comment on existing ones. Proposed potential sites are automatically added to the decision supporting tool's map.

Component (3b) was added this year along with various new spatial data layers relevant to the Israeli case study.

The Beta version of the innovative tool was delivered by M24 and feedback from all teams assisted in revising and improving the tool for this round of implementation. In M27, series of workshops were held in the Zoom platform for all team representatives to localize the tool for individual case studies. The SPOT-IT tool's Administrator Instructions document on how to localize the tool was delivered by the end of M30. The final submission is planned for M32.

Figure 1. Logical block scheme of the SPOT-IT tool

3.2 Advancement of SPOT-IT technology and new components

During 2022, the beta version of SPOT-IT was designed and launched for testing for the consortium members and designated experts. The enhanced functionality has enabled sufficient promotion of the tool as outlined below.

- 1) Integrating additional GIS layers that reflect the environmental carrying capacity of the case study area. These layers indicate the ecological fragility and vulnerability in terms of wildlife, biodiversity, and landscape in the case study area.
- 2) Employing big data methods to analyze images and texts retrieved from social media and social networks. The images were analyzed via a machine learning algorithm, and machine tags were attached to each image. Based on these results we performed sentiment analysis on the content to assign the photograph as positive/neutral/negative. Where available, we extracted the country and city of the user from their social media profile, where this data was not available, we developed an algorithm to estimate the home country based on the user's public photograph library. We have taken steps to ensure the results have no privacy concerns, we encrypted the user ID so no user can be identified to create a sentiment analysis-based layer and landscape characterization layer. These layers were added to the tool. For the photograph extraction we wrote code in the 'R' programming language to communicate with the Flickr API and download photograph. We then used PostGIS to extract photographs within the boundary of the study area. We extracted home location from the

public profile of users with code in the 'R' programming language to communicate with the Flickr API. To extract the tags from the images, we used the Google Cloud Vision API with code written in the 'R' programming language. For the sentiment analysis of tags, we used the NRC Emotion Lexicon again with code written in the 'R' programming language. The sentiment analysis-based map may help realize the general disposition towards a specific location as well as to better understand what are the specific characteristics that endow a tourism site with high ranking/positive reviews or sentiment. An interesting insight for example, that was derived from the sentiment map, is the incongruence between the high ranking on Google and TripAdvisor reviews and the sometimes-unsatisfied sentiment on the image sentiments analyses as reflected on the following map. While Gan-Guru Zoo and nearby Gan Ha'shlosa National Park have both high ranking on Google and TripAdvisor reviews (4.5 stars), Gan-Guru have lots of images with a negative attitude, whereas nearby Gan Ha'shlosa have almost only positive images.

Figure 2. The sentiment analysis-based map

- 3) We tested the tool in search of faults and bugs.

This process was carried as a feedback loop mechanism in which the teams provided continuous feedback, report on problems and faults, suggested ways to improve the tool and communicated their case-study's specific needs and requirements.

- 4) We have carried on two hands-on, online, workshops for all partners aimed at providing guidance of how to build the tool and issued a 'Tool's administrator instructions' in PDF.
- 5) We have started a dissemination process of the tool among the officials of the regional council and municipality that consist of the case study. Our intention is that the tool will be employed to its full potential and will be updated regularly.

4 Deliverables

4.1 SPOT-IT tools and manuals

SPOT-IT tool

The online SPOT-IT tool:

<https://gis.spotit.site/portal/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=f8d1ba98020646488a13d2ff6dd4392c>

Public engagement platform

The Cultural Heritage sites - Community Collaboration app, is a web/mobile app intended for the general public, it enables community members, stakeholders, or whoever wants to suggest potential cultural heritage sites. Submitted potential sites are automatically added to the decision supporting tool's map.

You can try it here: <https://arcg.is/05aCru>

SPOT-IT User Manual

SPOT-IT tool's explanatory notes:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ibtYe48PBK9-0kPDCIdVrB_76zf1yTwS3TF_scRyA0M/edit?usp=sharing

Video tutorial

A video clip with an explanation how the SPOT-IT tool operates:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7jOe4KOTavc&feature=youtu.be>

Localizing the tool – Tool's administrator instructions

The SPOT-IT tool's Administrator Instructions document can be found here:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Av8MQ0DcKf8E5a3OCrUDubFv9RVcNhcs90y1t7ILJ6E/edit?usp=sharing>

Localizing the tool - Hands-on workshop video

Here you can find the Hands-on workshop Zoom recording:

https://us02web.zoom.us/rec/play/Jt9oVa_HfvG35YgL2momPwahrY9A8mJ6JYLoczCfkJB1Hw-xPJzLRzJfITX1W4ibAh7bOuROF2AV5mNf.cbZUPJzw9i4iW-NK?autoplay=true&startTime=1646914489000